

Project: 101108469 — PreMETS — ERASMUS-EDU-2022-PI-ALL-INNO

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Predictive Maintenance Education & Training System: An alliance for boosting the European Innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education, and training

Project Acronym: **PreMETS**

Project Title: **Predictive Maintenance Education & Training System: An alliance for boosting the European Innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education, and training**

Project Number: **101108469**

Topic: **ERASMUS-EDU-2022-PI-ALL-INNO-EDU-ENTERP**

Type of Action: **ERASMUS-LS**

D7.2 Communication infrastructures

Final

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Author name(s):	Vasileios Tsoulis (YET)
Reviewer(s):	Athanasios Panagiotidis (YET)
Nature:	☒ R – Report P – Prototype ☐ D – Demonstrator ☐ O - Other
Dissemination level:	☒ PU – Public CO - Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission) RE - Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document history			
Version	Date	Modified by (author/partner)	Comments
1.1	27/09/2023	Vasileios Tsoulis (YET)	

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Website

The website will cater for the project’s web presence and branding. The website is developed in WordPress. YET will create all necessary pages and sections according to the project’s needs and instructions from the stakeholders during the whole course of the undertaking.

Website url: www.premets.eu

Website screen

Social Media (SM)

Social Media (SM) accounts were set up by YET and will be maintained by YET with the collaboration and support of the consortium. The consortium has agreed that YET will have administration rights for managing the project's Facebook and LinkedIn accounts. The purpose of utilizing the aforementioned platforms is to create additional channels of dissemination and communication with the public and the project's consortium. All partners will be contributing social media content (each will be responsible for one month in rotation) and YET will handle scheduling posts.

Social Media	Email / URL
Email	info@premets.eu
Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/premetseu/
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/100067569

PreMETS Facebook account screenshots (Premets)

PreMETS LinkedIn account screenshot (PreMETS)

Project logo and visual themes and guidelines

PreMETS logo brief

With our logo design we tried to encapsulate the essence of Predictive Maintenance and the mission of the PreMETS project. It's not just a logo; it's a visual representation of progress, trust, and innovation in the world of maintenance and technology. We believe this logo will leave a lasting impression and resonate with your target audience, furthering the goals of the project.

Logo Concept

Icon: The Abstract Soundwave

Our icon, an abstract soundwave, is a perfect representation of Acoustic Analysis Monitoring – one of the key methods of Predictive Maintenance. It visually signifies the data and information extracted from machinery sounds, which plays a vital role in maintaining equipment health. The dynamic and flowing form of the soundwave symbolizes the continuous monitoring and real-time analysis that are at the heart of Predictive Maintenance.

Color Palette: Light Green and Blue

The choice of colors is deliberate and meaningful:

Light Green: This color represents growth, innovation, and sustainability. It's the color of progress, indicating how Predictive Maintenance fosters sustainable development by reducing downtime and resource wastage.

Blue: Blue signifies trust, reliability, and technology. It symbolizes the dependable nature of Predictive Maintenance in ensuring machinery operates smoothly and efficiently.

Typography: Montserrat

We've selected Montserrat as the font for the wordmark because it's clean, modern, and highly legible. Its geometric shapes reflect precision, which aligns with the accuracy and efficiency inherent in Predictive Maintenance. The use of a consistent font creates a harmonious balance between the icon and the project name.

Overall Justification:

Our logo design is a visual testament to the core values and objectives of the PreMETS project:

Innovation: The abstract soundwave icon represents cutting-edge technology and the innovative approach of Predictive Maintenance.

Sustainability: The light green color signifies the project's commitment to sustainable practices in maintenance.

Reliability: The blue color instills trust, emphasizing the reliability of Predictive Maintenance in ensuring equipment longevity.

Education and Training: The acronym "PreMETS" in Montserrat font underscores the project's focus on education and training, empowering individuals and organizations with the skills needed for Predictive Maintenance.

Logo:**Templates****PPT template**

YET has created a PPT and a booklet template to be used by all partners for unofficial internal and official external usage. The same motives, design, colors as with the Project outlook (website, social media etc) have been used.

PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE EDUCATION & TRAINING SYSTEM

An alliance for boosting the European Innovation in
Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial
cooperation, education, and training

[Power Point template, cover page]

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- Mission
- Milestone
- Our Team
- Stay inspired. Never stop creating.
- Our Service
- The Process
- Market Analysis
- Our Goals
- Our Project
- Contact

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MANY THANKS

+123-your phone
hello@youremail.com
www.yourwebsite.com

[Power Point template, slides]

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